

Basics of Qualitative Research in Social Sciences: Analysis and Paradigms

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Abstract

In recent times, Qualitative Research as an ideal research methodology has been popular in the arena of social sciences. When we undergo any kind of research project in social sciences then we usually present qualitative data (tables, numbers, diagrams, figures) but this aims not at discrediting quantitative research but rather to emphasize the fact that this one finds its well-deserved place in the research field and in qualitative research. During the last few decades, qualitative research methodology is being pursued in a number of institutions since this methodology is ideal for analyzing human behaviour. My present paper makes an endeavour to highlight the basics of 'Qualitative Research Methodology in Social Sciences' with some of its allied domains with enough significance.

Keywords: *Qualitative Research; Ethnography; Narrative Approach; Grounded Theory; Survey Method.*

Introduction

To begin with fundamental conception of qualitative research it must be noted that it is an effective model occurring in natural setting and enabling the researcher to develop a level of detailing from high involvement in the actual experience [Creswell: 2009]. This particular methodology consists of a set of interpretive material practices that makes the world visible. It is a kind of multi-method in focus, engulfing an interpretive and naturalistic approach to the subject matter of research [Denzin and Lincoln,; 2005]. It observes and interprets people's perspective on different issues and analyzes them within a natural setting.

Qualitative Research Methodology comprises of a set of methods like logic, ethnography, discourse analysis, case-study, interview, counseling therapy, grounded theory, biography, comparative study, introspection, focus group, literary criticism, meditation practice, historical research etc. As a matter of fact, Qualitative Research is a kind of social action for interpreting experiences and social realities of individuals. It employs

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several methods like interviews, diaries, journals, classroom observations and to explain ‘How’ and ‘Why’ a particular social phenomenon operates making the social world wherein we inhabit more understandable for us.

Thus, this particular research methodology has gained its increased significance within social domain. It offers a deep insight of human behaviour, perspectives, feelings, experiences, attitudes, and emotions. Its chief paradigms are positivist, interpretive and critical paradigms exploring social realities and descriptions of the lived experiences of human beings. It is pursued in such areas like education, healthcare, nursing, sociology, anthropology, psychology, management and information systems etc. [Denzin and Lincoln:2005]. This methodology does not employ any statistical analysis or empirical calculation; its roots are embedded in social and cultural anthropology, philosophy, psychology, history and sociology. It aims at a ‘deep understanding of the particular [Domholdt: 1993], describing and parallel interpreting social issues systematically from the perspectives of individuals or population under study and hereby, stipulating new concepts and theories. The choice of methodology is directed by the questions being raised [Viswambharan: 2016]. With the increased usage of this methodology in scientific communities, controversies have been generated regarding epistemological, philosophical and methodological issues.

A Brief Overview

Following some research experts let us have a brief look at fundamental features of Qualitative Research Methodology.

- a) Burns and Grove [2009] have opined that qualitative research is a systematic and subjective approach to focus on and explain daily life experiences by attaching to them appropriate meanings.
- b) Qualitative Research Methodology has encompassed different histories namely (i) conceptual, (ii) interval, (iii) marginalizing, (iv) repressed, (v) social and (vi) technological histories [Brinkman .et.al:2014]
- c) The ideal structure of any qualitative research involves the following points viz. (i) the relevant literature studied (ii) characteristics and qualities studied (iii) description of the methodology (iv) statistical analysis and (v) conclusion regarding

the findings of the research [Williams: 2007].

- d) J. A. Hatch [2002] identifies five research paradigms: positivist, post-positivist, constructivist, critical/feminist and post-structuralist - all posing ontological, epistemological and methodological questions.

Objectives of the Present Paper

My present paper aims at expounding a transparent and clear picture of Qualitative Research Methodology in social sciences for the budding researchers. To this end, this study scrutinizes the following points.

- (i) Offering a preliminary conception of Qualitative Research Methodology.
- (ii) Ideal way of conducting Qualitative Research in social sciences.
- (iii) Various types of Qualitative Research Methodology.
- (iv) Emphasis is laid upon the characteristics, strengths and weakness, advantages and significance of Qualitative Research.

Historical origin of Qualitative Research Methodology

Any Research work is grounded in the theory of knowledge which begins with review of literature and new ideas. Social scientists study human behaviour not in laboratory but within the context of society. They create new trends, new mind-set beneficial for human society. Now, scientific research demands reliability, validity, demonstrability of data /facts.

However, ethical neutrality i.e. total unbiased-ness and ability to replicate can be easily attained in case of scientific research whereas in cases of social science research these are difficult to attain. Anthropologists and sociologists first used Qualitative Research as a method of inquiry in the early phase of twentieth century. The period from 1900 to 1945 is better known as traditional age of Qualitative Research. During this period, qualitative data analysis offered descriptive analysis of social phenomena. However, major works on this particular methodology like writing text books started in the period 1960 to 1970 and this period which marks out the second phase of evolution is called the golden age of qualitative research and has also exposed modern approach to this field of study. During this phase, data analysis was motivated chiefly by various ways of coding for materials obtained through observation. The symbolic

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interaction perspective, the origination of grounded theory and ethnographic study initiated the modern age of Qualitative Research.

Between 1970 and 1986 a variety of new interpretive qualitative perspectives like hermeneutics, structuralism, semiotics, phenomenology, cultural studies and feminism evolved. However, the post modern period of qualitative research began from 1990 and lasted till the end of 1995. This phase is remarkable for conducting new experiments and ethnographic studies. Then narratives replaced theories, or rather, so to say, narratives are rewritten as theories. The post-experimental phase spanned from 1995 to 2000. During this period, Qualitative Research emphasized more on the interpretation of democratic policies. The methodologically contested period ranged from 2000 to 2010 and is characterized by further establishment of Qualitative Research through various new journals [Denzin and Lincoln: 2005].

Research Methodology

Any type of research work, whether it be scientific or social science research, is required to follow specific methods / methodology in order to obtain solution of the research problem. Time limit, cost evaluation and budgeting are other crucial aspects of conducting research. Research methodology encompasses four types of question i.e. how, what and why, when, and where. Essential steps of social science research methodology are as follows;

- i) Objectivity,
- ii) Selection of topic,
- iii) Review of literature,
- iv) Follow up of appropriate methodology,
- v) Identification of area of interest,
- vi) Formation of hypothesis,
- vii) Data collection,
- viii) Data analysis,
- ix) Results and discussion,
- x) Application of research outcome.

Qualitative Research and its Varieties

At this point of discussion, we need to take a brief survey of types of Qualitative Research as following:

- i) **Narrative Research:** This method provides an analysis of the narrative text characteristics in terms of inter-human relations against the backdrop of their social, historical, and cultural contexts. It concentrates on people's narratives either about themselves or about a particular array of events; it also concentrates upon the sequential unfolding of someone's story. This process is enough time consuming and usually is capable of covering only a limited number of cases. A doctor's way of treating his patients is one of the examples of narrative research.
- ii) **Phenomenological Research:** Phenomenon is basically an intrinsic awareness of one's own self. It is a kind of subjective experience. This approach is accepted when the researcher intends to study life experiences of a concept or phenomenon experienced by one or more individuals or such areas wherein the research has got very little knowledge. For example, a researcher takes interview of 100 widows and asks them to narrate their experiences about the death of their husbands.
- iii) **Grounded Theory:** This theory was developed in 1967. By two sociologists Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss in their book titled "The Discovery of Grounded Theory". In this approach, the researcher tries to formulate a general abstract theory of a particular process, action or interaction by taking the views of the participants under study. It makes use of both inductive and deductive approach for theory development. This theory gives stress upon the inclusion of 5 different aspects of research namely (i) description of the research questions (ii) literature review (iii) describing the methodology (iv) data analysis explaining the theory and finally, (v) discussing the implications. We can enumerate some of its key features as follows:
 - (a) It focuses on emergence of absolutely novel concepts from collected data.
 - (b) It bases its sampling process solely on theoretically relevant constructs.

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- (c) It also employs constant cooperative method which is a useful formulation of law to do qualitative analysis and can be used separately from the other elements of grounded theory.
- (d) It requires the sanctity of theoretical sensitivity.
- (iv) **Action Research:** This type of qualitative research compiles both theory and action to integrate knowledge with already existing organizational knowledge. Also, it addresses real organizational problems together with the participants under study.
- (v) **Case Study:** It is an exhaustive description of an individual case and its analysis- “A case study is used when we analyze and describe each person individually for his/her own activity, special needs, life situation, life history etc.” [Sagadin: 1995]. Thus. “Case study is an in-depth exploration from multiple perspectives of the complexity and uniqueness of a particular project, policy, institution, program or system in a real life” [Simons: 2009].

Case study is usually the study of a single case or a very limited number of cases. Depending on the purpose of study, the researcher may follow either qualitative or quantitative research design. Case study approach, in its turn, engulfs several types like, retrospective case study, snapshot study, diachronic study, nested study, sequential study etc.

However, this method is very time-consuming and too costly. It is used to study one or more cases within a bounded setting or context by means of multiple sources like questionnaires, interviews, observations, written accounts and audio-visual materials. In spite of all its drawbacks, this method is followed profusely in subjects like sociology and practice-oriented fields like management, public administration, psychology, history, education and medicine.

- (vi) **Ethnographic Research:** It aims at studying beliefs, social interactions and behaviours of small societies after observing all these over a certain time period and the bases of the data collected [Denzin and Lincoln: 2011]. The fundamental point of difference between case study and ethnographic study revolves around the fact that while case study studies a particular program or event or person over long period of time, ethnographic study concentrates on

a group sharing a common culture. Following Lecompte and Schensul [1999: 210-211] we can make up a brief checklist of the features of this particular research design:

- (i) It involves direct interaction between the researcher and the participants.
- (ii) It is reflective of the participants' perspectives and behaviors.
- (iii) This method is followed within a natural setup and not within laboratory.
- (iv) It makes use of multiple data collection tools and techniques.
- (v) It attempts to make a critical evaluation of all human behaviors and beliefs against their socio-political and historical surroundings.
- (vi) It treats the concept of culture as a medium for interpreting its findings.

But this method of study is also time-taking as well as laborious for the researcher.

- (vii) **Historical Research:** As the name suggests historical research studies a particular phenomenon through the lenses of its history. Consequently, this method is also known as historiography i.e. investigation of elements from history. It is a systematic way of collecting past data and identifying, classifying, arranging, clarifying, evaluating, synthesizing, elaborating, developing, and publishing them by means of scientific techniques.

The sources of historical data may be classified as follows;
[Danto:2008]

- a) Primary sources i.e. original documents collected from archives.
- b) Secondary sources i.e. writings of different historians
- c) Official records gathered from various institutions and case reports.
- d) Private materials like chronicles, autobiographies, diaries,

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memoirs, records etc.

External criticism i.e. checking the authenticity or genuineness of the data collected and internal criticism i.e. verifying the accuracy of the data collected after its authenticity being proved are two primal modes of evaluating data collected through historical study. External criticism attaches validity to the data whereas internal criticism proves their reliability.

Following are some of the aims of this method:

- a) Exploring the unknown.
- b) Analyzing such events the consequences of which can be verified since the past to present days.
- c) Dealing with those issues that have not been properly resolved till date.

(viii) Content Analyses: It is a way of analyzing and interpreting written, verbal or visual communication messages. Data collection, in this particular method of study, is carried out in two distinct steps:

- a) The researcher does analysis and presents them in the form of a frequency table and
- b) the researcher also does statistical analysis to represent data in quantitative format. Initial coding, content analysis and summative analysis are its three major approaches.\

Strengths and Weaknesses of Qualitative Research

Following Yauch and Stendel [2003:117] and Creswell [2014:90] we can enumerate the following key major strengths of this research methodology.

- a) Open-minded questioning reveals new or unanticipated phenomena thus generating several other new novel issues that require open-minded inquiry.
- b) Its participants include cross sectional mob of the society.
- c) It is a detailed analysis of affected populations.
- d) Without employing any statistical method it gains insight about its research area through descriptive, narrative style.
- e) It is suggestive of possible relationships, causes, effects and dynamic processes.

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- f) It encourages creative and innovative explanatory frameworks.
- g) Data analyst remains pre-occupied with data collection and knows its strength.

Again we can note down the following key points of weaknesses of this research methodology.

- a) It fails to demonstrate the rigour of scientific data collection process.
- b) Because of its broad-minded questionnaire tools the participants gain more control over the content of the data collected.
- c) It lacks an infinite and preconceived set of issues to explore.
- d) Its collected data are not empirically verifiable and also time-consuming and costly.
- e) It employs laborious analysis techniques like categorization, recording.
- f) The perspectives of both researcher and participants may be biased and
- g) Finally, because of its subjective approach its collected data cannot be tested through the lenses of the standards of reliability and validity.

The ideal method of research: Qualitative or Quantitative?

Quantitative and qualitative facts are representatives of the same reality. So, there remains no question of ignoring any one of them; any one of them is not superior to the other one. This argument became popular during the last twenty years. The kind of research one is pursuing determines which one of the two available methodologies is to be applied. Humanistic approach evolves as a pure transformation of scientific approach. Humanistic approach is equivalent to qualitative research methodology. A good researcher must master the art of handling words generated out of qualitative research and numbers generated out of quantitative research because of three vital reasons; i) Numbers are to be interpretative coming from cultural practices and it has to be qualitative in nature; ii) Qualitative research is impressionistic. It is one of its major drawbacks. It can be overcome if and only if human behaviour is countable in terms of numbers which are to be quantitatively interpreted. Any research must be original, persuasive and depending upon this researcher may employ either the

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repository of qualitative or quantitative research. The second point encompasses the following four different aspects, namely: a) Each discipline has got its own notion of reality which can be studied and interpreted numerically (Ontological aspect). b) Both observer and the observed in research carry their own social baggage like social identities, cultural heritage which are capable of influencing communication, orientations as well as the aspect that the researcher may intend to study (Epistemological aspect). c) Human researchers doing researches even upon non human subjects cannot go beyond their value systems (Axiological aspect) and d) Methodological aspect i.e. how we are going to collect data; iii) Contemplative writing and research writing include observation which is a kind of conscious sensing. Research is all concerned with ideas that may come at any point of time. Karl Popper once remarked that all researches are made of certain problem solution which is to be pursued till the end. Observation procedure is one of the chief methods of data collection. Interview is another crucial research technique. Survey method, field work, stipulation of questionnaire, experimentation are several vital tools of data collection all having their ontological realities, epistemological view points, value frameworks as well as relevance to specific disciplines. So, now after going through all these points it can be logically concluded that neither qualitative nor quantitative method all alone is ideal for conducting research work. Both the methodologies in spite of having completely different theoretical orientation can be successfully combined for an enriched understanding of the phenomenon under study. To put in other words, a combination of both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies should be ideal for the successful completion of any kind of research work.

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